

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In reply refer to:
08FBDT00-2017-F-0023-1

April 23, 2021

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450 Golden Gate Avenue
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Subject: Reinitiation of Formal Consultation on the Chevron Pipeline Bay Area Product Line Richmond-Bethany Pipeline Repair Project, Contra Costa County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers [Corps] file number: 2016-00279S)

Dear Dr. Galacatos:

This letter is in response to the Corps' March 15, 2021, letter requesting reinitiation of consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the Chevron Pipeline Bay Area Product Line (BAPL) Richmond-Bethany Pipeline Repair Project in Contra Costa County, California. At issue for this reinitiation are including two additional repair sites and the associated effects on the endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)¹, soft bird's-beak (*Cordylanthus mollis spp. mollis*), and salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*). This document is issued under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

On March 2, 2017 the Service issued a concurrence that the BAPL Richmond-Bethany Pipeline Repair Project was not likely to adversely affect the threatened California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*), California clapper rail, and soft's bird's-beak and issued a biological opinion for the salt marsh harvest mouse.

Eight of the eleven pipeline repairs in the March 2, 2017 consultation were completed in 2018. Three of the repairs (2014-RA-002, 2014-RA-003, and 2014-RA-010) were not completed, and the Chevron Pipe Line Company has determined that they are no longer necessary and will not be completed. Two new repair sites have been identified: 2020-RA-001 and 2020-RA-002.

¹ Until the Service officially adopts recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union to Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence. Note, the change in taxonomic assignment does not change the listing status of the species.

Repair 2020-RA-001 is located approximately 980 feet south of the previously authorized repair 2014-RA-002 and repair 2020-RA-002 is approximately 980 feet north of the previously authorized repair 2014-RA-003. The Corps has determined these additions may affect but are not likely to adversely affect the soft bird's-beak or California clapper rail, is likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse, and will have no effect on the California red-legged frog. The previous consultation request included a request for concurrence of not likely to adversely affect the California red-legged frog.

In reviewing this reinitiation request, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' March 15, 2021 consultation request letter and enclosed February 2021 *Supplemental Biological Assessment* (Supplemental BA); (2) the Service's March 2, 2017 biological opinion; and (3) other information available to the Service.

After further review, the Service does not concur that the actions in Wildcat Marsh are not likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail due to noise, visual, and potential habitat disturbance. The remainder of this document is the amended informal on the soft bird's-beak and California red-legged frog and formal consultation on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail in full. Additions are underlined and deletions are in ~~strikethrough~~. Aspects of the project that have already occurred will remain without changes including the previous California red-legged frog concurrence.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the soft bird's-beak because: (1) no soft bird's-beak have been observed during surveys in 2013 and 2015 or along the pipeline alignment during surveys conducted during the appropriate blooming period (July-November) for previous pipeline repair projects located in Wildcat Marsh; (2) a Service-approved biologist will conduct rare plant surveys in the Action Area and implement conservation measures; and (3) no mortality or occupied habitat loss is expected. If soft bird's-beak is observed during surveys, reinitiation of consultation may be necessary as implementation of conservation measures proposed in the Supplemental BA may result in adverse effects.

~~The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail because: (1) project activities are temporary and short-term; (2) the area of habitat disturbance is limited to pickleweed (i.e. 0.19 acre at 2014-RA-003 and minimal pickleweed habitat at RA-002 (3) no permanent habitat loss is expected because repair sites will be restored to pre-construction conditions according to the Site Restoration Plan; (4) construction will occur in the non-breeding season of September 1 through January 31; (5) if construction during the nesting season (February 1 through August 31) is unavoidable, daily surveys of the work area and an additional 700-foot zone around the work area would be conducted each morning prior to starting work; and (6) a Service-approved biologist will monitor proposed project construction.~~

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California red-legged frog because: (1) the site does not provide suitable breeding habitat; (2) Byron Highway imposes a barrier to dispersal and occurs between the area of known occurrence and the project site; (3) preconstruction surveys will be conducted; and (4) exclusion fencing will be installed at the end of the work day to ensure no amphibians move into work areas.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Chevron Pipe Line Company (CPL) proposes to investigate and replace/repair specific anomalies in the BAPL Sacramento leg of the pipeline that could have compromised pipeline integrity. Such inspections and repairs are necessary to comply with State and Federal regulations and standards for pipelines transporting hazardous liquids. Pipeline repairs are proposed for the winter of 2016, ~~and~~ spring/summer of 2017, ~~and~~ 2021. The pipeline wall thickness is potentially compromised in areas identified as an anomaly. Due to uncertainty of the extent of severity of anomalies, CPL has prioritized the investigations to ensure that all pipeline repairs will be made in a timely manner. The project footprint for each repair site varies based on the method of repair or replacement proposed. The information provided by the in-line inspection (ILI) tool for each anomaly dictates the potential footprint for the exploratory dig and includes information regarding the thickness of pipe indicating the potential severity of damage; however, extent and severity of the damage approximated by the ILI tool must be validated by excavating the pipeline and inspecting the anomaly for the repair method. The proposed footprint provided for each repair site in the BA was an estimate based on information provided by the ILI tool along with knowledge from previous repairs/replacements conducted in similar areas. Due to the unknown condition of the pipeline, CPL proposes to excavate a larger area than needed to allow for flexibility in project planning and to account for any unforeseen issues once the pipeline is exposed and the anomaly identified. Impact footprints will be limited to the minimum necessary for safe completion of the investigation and repair may be less than the impact area proposed.

Construction Access – Existing roads will be used to the extent possible to access repair sites. ~~2104 RA-002 and RA-003~~ 2020-RA-001 and 2020-RA-002 are located within Wildcat (Chevron) Marsh adjacent to the West County Wastewater Treatment Plant (WCWTP). Access to ~~2104 RA-002 and RA-003~~ 2020-RA-001 will occur through the Wildcat Creek Trailhead Parking Lot, utilizing a paved roadway and a constructed berm. Site 2020-RA-002 access will occur through WCWTP from ~~Pittsburg Avenue~~ and Garden Tract Road. From WCWTP, equipment will access the repairs from a paved road adjacent to Wildcat Marsh. From the paved road, DURA-BASE® composite interlocking mats will be used to provide safe equipment access through the marsh to the repair sites while limiting ground disturbance within the marsh.

Repair sites 2014-RA-005 and RA-006 are located behind an industrial complex on Goodrick Road. Access to the two repair sites will occur from Goodrick Road and the industrial complex's parking lot. Repair sites 2014-RA-007 through ~~RA-009~~ RA-010 are located within an undeveloped portion of Richmond and will occur from Goodrick Avenue. 2014-RA-022 is located behind a storage facility on Pacheco Boulevard with access through an adjacent business. 2014-RA-023 is located in an undeveloped area immediately east of Interstate 680 and access will occur from an adjacent parking area. 2014-RA-027 is located in an agricultural ditch and

access will occur from the shoulder of Byron Highway. Access routes will be approximately twelve feet wide. No ground disturbance will be required to establish access to the repair sites.

Staging Area – Minimal equipment is necessary to complete the repairs and only a small, dedicated staging area is needed at each site. All staging areas and vehicle parking will be located within uplands whenever possible. Where possible, staging areas will be located within previously disturbed areas near the project sites.

Construction Equipment and Techniques – In order to determine the exact location of the repair site, CPL must conduct a series of verification digs on the pipeline near the repair sites. The verification digs involve excavation of the pipeline at a minimum of two locations and maximum of four locations within the pipeline easement to visually locate an identifying feature on the pipeline (e.g. joint weld, pipeline bend, pipe pup, etc.). All verification digs are hand excavated and situated in upland habitat when possible. Repair site 2020-RA-001 is not expected to need a verification dig due to the anomaly's conspicuous location on a field marked bend in the pipeline. Running parallel to the BAPL at both repair 2020-RA-001 and 002 sites is another utility pipeline that will be exposed to verify its location during repair activities. This process, also known as utility potholing, is important for safety while excavating.

Once the exact position of the anomaly is determined, the anomaly will be excavated by hand until the pipeline is located. The remaining trench will be excavated with a rubber-tired backhoe. The upper six inches of soil will be stockpiled separately and placed over the top of backfilled soil to maintain the integrity of the soil profile and preserve the existing seedbank. The excavation width at most of the sites will be twelve feet to allow for benching. The excavation length varies depending on the length of the anomaly. The trench depth varies by repair location, but is typically approximately six feet deep to fully expose the pipeline. Once the pipeline is fully exposed and the anomaly is identified and analyzed, pipeline repair activities could include a re-coat of protective epoxy, installation of a clock-spring, installation of a steel sleeve, or a cut-out and replacement of a pipeline section. Once pipeline repairs are completed, the trench will be backfilled and re-contoured to pre-construction conditions. Restoration of wetland areas will include topsoil separation and replacement to pre-construction topography. Pickleweed removed for access or excavation will be returned as mulch upon completion of the repair.

Repair Site Remediation – To prevent erosion, upland portions of the site will be hydroseeded with a native plant seed mix appropriate for the site. Restoration of wetland areas will include topsoil separation and replacement to pre-construction topography. For repair sites ~~2014-RA-002 and RA-003~~ 2020-RA-001 and 2020-RA-002, pickleweed removed for access or excavation will be returned as mulch upon completion of the repair.

Duration of Temporary Impacts – All project activities are temporary with no permanent loss of habitat. The repair locations will be fully restored to pre-construction conditions.

Conservation Measures

General Avoidance and Minimization Measures for All Listed Species

1. All CPL employees and contractors involved with the project will be required to attend a threatened and endangered species education program developed by biologists, focusing on the listed species covered in this document. All contractors and employees will receive formal training prior to working on site. At a minimum, the program will cover species distribution, identification characteristics, sensitivity to human activities, legal protection, penalties for violation of State and Federal laws, reporting requirements, and project avoidance, minimization, and mitigation measures.
2. A qualified biological monitor will be on site during all ground-disturbing activities. The monitor will inform the construction foreman of the need to halt construction in the event a listed species is observed. In addition, prior to construction activities each day, a qualified biological monitor shall inspect excavations to ensure no wildlife is trapped or hiding within the excavation.
3. A pre-construction survey will be conducted by a qualified biologist immediately prior to the start of construction at each site to ensure that there are no sensitive species present in the work area.
4. Trenches will be covered or have escape ramps installed overnight to prevent unintentional entrapment of wildlife.
5. Standard best management practices, such as the use of silt fencing and straw wattles, will be implemented to avoid increased turbidity and sedimentation to nearby waterways at the repair sites.
6. All vehicle traffic will use established roadways and approved access routes. Overland travel will be prohibited unless pre-established and approved by a qualified biologist. All vehicles will maintain a speed limit 10 miles per hour on all access roads.
7. Trash and food items will be kept in closed containers and removed daily to prevent attracting wildlife to the site.
8. Firearms and pets will be prohibited at all project sites.
9. Construction vehicles and equipment will be repaired and refueled a minimum of 100 feet from wetlands or waterways to the maximum extent feasible. If refueling or repairing equipment or vehicles in or within close proximity to wetlands is unavoidable, appropriate secondary spill containment will be used to prevent spills in sensitive habitats.
10. Any spills of hazardous materials in sensitive habitat will be immediately cleaned up and removed.
11. Encounters with listed species will be reported immediately to the onsite qualified biologist and reported to the Service and Corps within 24 hours. The biologist will maintain records of all listed species encountered during project activities, including the

following information:

- location
- habitat type
- date of observation
- general condition and health
- apparent injuries and state of healing
- if moved, location moved to
- diagnostic markings (e.g., identification number)

12. In the event that a dead or injured listed species is observed on the project site during construction activities, notification will be made within 24 hours to the Service and Corps, as appropriate. If the species is also protected by the California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW), the CDFW will be notified within 24 hours of the observation. Any listed species injured through CPL's activities will be transported to a Lindsay Wildlife Hospital in Walnut Creek or an approved wildlife veterinarian at CPL's expense.
13. After repair activities are complete, the project site and all disturbed areas will be seeded or hydroseeded with a native seed mix. Note: Sites with pickleweed or emergent vegetation have specific restoration requirements and will not be restored using hydroseeding techniques.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Chevron Pipe Line Company and its contractors will implement the following conservation measures to avoid and minimize adverse effects to the salt marsh harvest mouse:

1. Work will be scheduled to avoid extreme high tides when there is potential for salt marsh harvest mice to move to higher, drier grounds. All equipment will be staged on existing roadways away from the project site when not in use.
2. Pickleweed will be avoided to the extent feasible in order to reduce potential impacts to the salt marsh harvest mouse. If pickleweed cannot be avoided, all pickleweed will be removed by hand. A Service-approved biological monitor will be on site to monitor all pickleweed removal activities.
3. Exclusion fencing for sites with a high potential for salt marsh harvest mouse will be installed around project work areas and access roads to limit the extent of ground disturbing activities and project impacts. The exclusion fencing will extend the length of the area where equipment and personnel are routinely active during construction. All exclusion fencing will consist of heavy-gauge plastic sheeting that will be a minimum of 12 inches taller than adjacent vegetation. The plastic sheeting will be installed between wooden stakes positioned no more than every 5 feet apart and fastened to the ground with landscaping staples at 3-inch intervals.

4. Excavation sites will be restored to their pre-construction conditions. The upper six inches of soil excavated within salt marsh harvest mouse habitat (i.e. pickleweed) will be stockpiled separately and replaced on top of the backfilled material. Areas where vegetation is removed will be restored to their original contours prior to topsoil placement. Vegetation removed from the site will be replaced on top of disturbed areas of the project site.

California Clapper Rail

1. Construction will occur during the California Ridgway's rail non-breeding season of September 1 through January 31. If construction during the nesting season (February 1 through August 31) is unavoidable, daily surveys will be conducted each morning prior to starting work. The survey area will include the work area and an additional 700-foot zone around the work area. If a California clapper rail (adult, juvenile, or nestling) or nest is located within the surveyed area, then no work will occur. If nestlings are present in the work area, no work will be conducted regardless of the survey results. If no nests are located by August 1, daily morning surveys will be discontinued provided there are no nestlings in the work area.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined as all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action (50 CFR 402.02). The Action Area for this section 7 consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the construction zone, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, or movement associated with the proposed project. The Action Area includes Chevron's excavation areas (trench and verification dig areas), temporary access roads and staging areas, and within 700 feet of salt marsh habitat.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. "Jeopardize the continued existence of" means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that

are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*). Both subspecies are listed as endangered. The status of the salt marsh harvest mouse and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf. Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

California Clapper Rail

Information about the California clapper rail biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

Surrounding Land Uses and Existing Conditions

The proposed project occurs along the BAPL between Richmond Refinery in Richmond and the

Bethany Reservoir, south of the town of Byron in Contra Costa County, California. It is located within the Central California Coast Section of the Coast Ranges geologic province. The alluvial plain is gently sloping to nearly level alluvial fans. The subsection elevation range is from sea level up to about 500 feet on hills along the Hayward Fault. Repairs located in Richmond are within the East Bay Terraces and Alluvium ecological subsection. Repair areas in Martinez and the repair located near Byron are within the Suisun Hills and Valley ecological subsection. All repair sites are within the pipeline easement. The land surrounding the pipeline easement is predominately undeveloped and the repair sites occur within agricultural land or conservation areas.

Land uses adjacent to repair sites are a mix of salt marsh, pasture, residential development, industrial areas, transportation infrastructure, and other infrastructure such as the West County Wastewater Treatment Plant.

Repair areas ~~2014-RA-002, RA-003~~ 2020-RA-001, 2020-RA-002, 2014-RA-006, and 2014-RA-023 are located in low, middle, or high brackish marsh zones. Vegetation is a dynamic continuum between the salt marshes of San Francisco Bay and freshwater tidal marshes of its major tributary rivers, fluctuating with variable influences including rainfall and freshwater discharges that alter marsh salinity gradients. Representative low brackish marsh plant species include alkali bulrush (*Scirpus maritimus*), California tule (*Scirpus californicus*), hardstem tule (*Scirpus acutus*), and cattails (*Typha* spp.). Middle brackish marsh zones are characterized by species such as pickleweed (*Salicornia pacifica*), alkali heath (*Frankenia salina*), California loosestrife (*Lythrum californicum*), spearscale (*Atriplex triangularis*), and salt rush (*Juncus balticus*). High brackish zone plant species include California blackberry (*Rubus ursinus*), toad rush (*Juncus bufonius*), yarrow (*Achillea millefolium*), salt marsh baccharis (*Baccharis pilularis*), and California bee plant (*Scrophularia californica*). 2020-RA-001 is located within the middle brackish marsh community. At this repair site the community was dominated by pickleweed and rye grass (*Festuca perennis*). 2020-RA-002 is also located within the middle brackish marsh zone and at this repair site the community was entirely dominated by pickleweed.

Freshwater emergent wetland is typically associated with topographic low areas such as ponds, channels, and lake or river margins. 2014-RA-022 is located within emergent wetland and is dominated by broad-leaved cattail (*Typha angustifolia*), common tule (*Schoenoplectus acutus*), and Himalayan blackberry (*Rubus armeniacus*).

2014-RA-005 is located in a small riparian area dominated by red willow (*Salix laevigata*) with flatsedge (*Cyperus eragrostis*). 2015-AB-027 is located within an agricultural ditch that ponds seasonally from rainfall and supports wetland vegetation dominated exclusively by perennial pepperweed (*Lepidium latifolium*).

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Salt marsh harvest mouse has been documented in Wildcat (Chevron) Marsh ~~at~~ near the locations of ~~2014-RA-002 and RA-003~~ 2020-RA-001 and 2020-RA-002. Extensive pickleweed occurs at ~~RA-003~~ 2020-RA-002 and the species is likely present. ~~RA-002~~ 2020-RA-001 is a combination of low amounts of pickleweed and ruderal vegetation. ~~RA-003 occurs near a previous repair that~~

was conducted in 2013 and no salt marsh harvest mice were observed during vegetation removal and exclusion fence installation. There is an occurrence within approximately 0.5 miles of RA-010 but there is currently no habitat within or adjacent to this project area to support the species. There is no pickleweed habitat at sites 2014-RA-005 through ~~RA-010~~ RA-009, RA-023, or 2015-AB-027.

California Clapper Rail

The Supplemental BA reports a California Natural Diversity Database occurrence within Wildcat Marsh near where 2020-RA-001 and 002 are located and observed during protocol presence/absence surveys conducted in 2013 for a previous pipeline repair project within the marsh (BIOMaAS 2013 as cited in the Supplemental BA). Multiple individuals of California clapper rail were identified within the marsh during protocol surveys and multiple individuals were heard in the distance during construction monitoring for that previous project. No rails were visually observed during execution of that project since vegetation was hand-cleared within the authorized disturbance area and visqueen exclusion fencing was installed to isolate the work area from the surrounding salt marsh habitat.

Effects of the Proposed Project

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail occurs primarily at ~~2014-RA-003~~ 2020-RA-002, with lower quality pickleweed and ruderal habitat occurring at ~~RA-002~~ 2020-RA-001. Completion of the repair at 2020 RA-002 will result in a temporary loss of 0.15 acre of pickleweed habitat and approximately 0.01 acre at 2020-RA-001. Project activities are considered temporary and short-term and the site will be restored to pre-construction conditions immediately after repairs have concluded. However, because the species occurs in pickleweed habitat, if salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rail are present, the species will be displaced to adjacent habitat during hand removal of vegetation. If mice or rails are displaced due to project activities, they would likely relocate to refugial habitat within extensive marsh and pickleweed cover in Wildcat Marsh. Noise and vibrations from construction activities and heavy equipment may result in the harassment disturbance of individual salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails in the adjacent salt marsh habitat and expose them to predation if they were flushed from cover or prevented from seeking available cover. Repairs at 2020-RA-001 and 002 are proposed to occur outside of the California clapper rail nesting season avoiding effects to breeding adults or nesting chicks. Whereas mortality is expected to be low because of hand removal of vegetation in excavation areas, some individuals could be accidentally harmed during digging with hand tools and heavy equipment.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. The Service is not aware of specific projects that might affect the salt marsh harvest mouse in the Action Area that are currently under review by State, county, or local authorities.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the salt marsh harvest mouse and the California clapper rail, the environmental baseline for the Action Area, the effects of the proposed action, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse and the California clapper rail. This is based on the size of the affected suitable habitat area, the fact that habitat disturbance will be temporary and short-term, and the implementation of conservation measures.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by the Service as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the Service to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicants to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual salt marsh harvest mice will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the proposed project as the following:

1. ~~Harassment, Harm, injury, and mortality of all salt marsh harvest mice within the 0.16 acre of suitable habitat of the 0.36 acre of potential habitat~~ as described in the Supplemental BA (0.17 acre in RA-002 and 0.19 acre in RA-003 0.15 acre in 2020-RA-002 and 0.01 acre in 2020-RA-001).
2. Harm from habitat modification of all California clapper rails within suitable habitat within the 0.16 acre of suitable habitat as described in the Supplemental BA and harm, by impairing essential behaviors such as breeding, foraging, or predator evasion, of all California clapper rails in the marsh habitat adjacent to the construction areas.

Upon implementation of the reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determines that the levels of take are not likely to result in jeopardy to the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

The following reasonable and prudent measures are necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project to the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail:

1. The Corps will minimize the potential for harm of the California clapper rail and harm ~~harassment~~, or mortality of salt marsh harvest mouse.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure that the applicants comply with the following terms and conditions, which implement their respective reasonable and prudent measures described above. These terms and conditions are non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The Corps shall minimize the potential for ~~harm, harassment, injury, killing or other forms of take of the salt marsh harvest mouse~~ incidental take from project related activities by implementation of the Conservation Measures as described in the Project

Description in this biological opinion or as modified by the Terms and Conditions of this document. As such the Corps, applicant, or contractors shall not handle or move listed species as described in Conservation Measure 11 under General Avoidance and Minimization Measures for All Listed Species.

- b. The Corps shall ensure that the applicants immediately notify the Service of any killed, injured, or entrapped salt marsh harvest mice, within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-~~5603~~ 2664.
- c. The Corps shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the Conservation Measures and Terms and Conditions in this biological opinion.
- d. The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the Conservation Measures were implemented for this project.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 2b, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, The Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the Disposition of Individuals Taken section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and California Natural Diversity Database (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).
3. The applicants shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within sixty (60) calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the salt

marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-5603 ~~2664~~; ~~and the Resident Agent in Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.~~

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in re-vegetation efforts.
2. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
3. Assist the Service in implementing other recovery actions identified within most current recovery plans for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes reinitiation of formal consultation for the Chevron Pipeline Bay Area Product Line (BAPL) Richmond-Bethany Pipeline Repair Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or

is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
 - (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
- (b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

If you have any question or concern regarding this response, please contact Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 08FBDT00-2017-F-0023-1 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Jana Affonso
Assistant Field Supervisor

LITERATURE CITED

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- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2013. Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California. Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. xviii + 605 pp.
https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf